

\mathcal{JP}^*O Sets in Intuitionistic Topological Spaces

*L. Jeyasudha¹, K. Bala Deepa Arasi²

¹Research Scholar, Reg. No: 20122012092004, PG & Research Department of Mathematics, A.P.C. Mahalaxmi College for Women, Thoothukudi, TN, India.

²Assistant Professor of Mathematics, A.P.C. Mahalaxmi College for Women, Thoothukudi, Tamilnadu, India.

*Corresponding author: L. Jeyasudha

Research Scholar, Reg. No: 20122012092004, PG & Research Department of Mathematics, A.P.C. Mahalaxmi College for Women, Thoothukudi, TN, India. Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, TN, India.

Abstract

The major goal of this work is to introduce the concepts of $\mathcal{J}g$ - closure operator and \mathcal{J} - interior operators to a new class of sets termed \mathcal{JP}^*O sets and \mathcal{JP}^*C sets in \mathcal{JTS} . Additionally, we define the \mathcal{JP}^*int and \mathcal{JP}^*cl operators in \mathcal{JTS} . We continue to look into the connection to \mathcal{JPO} sets in \mathcal{JTS} .

Keywords: \mathcal{JP}^*O sets, \mathcal{JP}^*C sets, \mathcal{JP}^*int operator, \mathcal{JP}^*cl operator.

AMS subject classification (2010): 54C05.

1. Introduction

D. Coker [1] introduced the idea of intuitionistic sets for the first time in 1996. 2016 saw the definition of intuitionistic pre open sets in \mathcal{JTS} by G. Sasikala and M. Navaneethakrishnan [4]. We define \mathcal{JP}^*O sets and \mathcal{JP}^*C sets in this study using the idea of $\mathcal{J}g$ - closure and \mathcal{J} - interior operators. We also look into the connection between \mathcal{JPO} and \mathcal{JP}^*O sets in \mathcal{JTS} .

In this study, a new class of \mathcal{JS} called \mathcal{JP}^*O sets is introduced. We also demonstrate that the class of \mathcal{JP}^*O sets is intermediate between the classes of \mathcal{JO} and \mathcal{JPO} sets.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 [1] Let \check{X}_J be a set that is not empty. An object with the form $M_J = \langle \check{X}_J, M_{J1}, M_{J2} \rangle$, where M_{J1} and M_{J2} are subsets of \check{X}_J satisfying $M_{J1} \cap M_{J2} = \phi$, is known as an *intuitionistic set* (\mathcal{JS} in short). The terms “set of members of M_J ” and “set of non-members of M_J ” refer to the sets M_{J1} and M_{J2} respectively.

Definition 2.2 [1] Assume that \check{X}_J is a non-empty set, that $M_J = \langle \check{X}_J, M_{J1}, M_{J2} \rangle$, that $N_J = \langle \check{X}_J, N_{J1}, N_{J2} \rangle$ is an \mathcal{JS} 's and that $\{M_{Ji} : i \in J\}$ be arbitrary family of \mathcal{JS} 's. Then the subsequent are holds.

- $M_J \subseteq N_J$ iff $M_{J1} \subseteq N_{J1}$ and $M_{J2} \supseteq N_{J2}$.
- $M_J = N_J$ iff $M_J \subseteq N_J$ and $M_J \supseteq N_J$.
- The complement of M_J is defined as $M_J^c = \langle \check{X}_J, M_{J2}, M_{J1} \rangle$.
- $\cup M_{Ji} = \langle \check{X}_J, \cup M_{Ji1}, \cap M_{Ji2} \rangle$.
- $\cap M_{Ji} = \langle \check{X}_J, \cap M_{Ji1}, \cup M_{Ji2} \rangle$.
- $M_J - N_J = M_J \cap N_J^c$.
- $\check{\phi}_I = \langle \check{X}_J, \phi, \check{X}_J \rangle$ and $\check{X}_I = \langle \check{X}_J, \check{X}_J, \phi \rangle$.

Definition 2.3 [1] Assume that \check{X}_J is a non-empty set and τ_I is the set of $\mathcal{J}S$'s of \check{X}_J then τ_I is known as an *intuitionistic topology* ($\mathcal{J}T$ in short) on \check{X}_J if it meets the criteria listed below:

- 1) $\check{X}_I, \check{\phi}_I \in \tau_I$.
- 2) $M_J \cap N_J \in \tau_I$ for every $M_J, N_J \in \tau_I$.
- 3) $\cup M_{J_i} \in \tau_I$ for any arbitrary family $\{M_{J_i} : i \in J\} \subseteq \tau_I$.

The pair (\check{X}_J, τ_I) is referred to as *intuitionistic topological space* ($\mathcal{J}TS$ in short) and intuitionistic open set ($\mathcal{J}OS$ in short) in \check{X}_J is referred to as $\mathcal{J}S$ in τ_I . The intuitionistic closed set ($\mathcal{J}CS$ in short) in \check{X}_J is regarded as the counterpart of $\mathcal{J}OS$ in \check{X}_J .

Definition 2.4 [1] Assume that \check{X}_J is a non-empty set and \hat{G}_I is the set of $\mathcal{J}S$'s of \check{X}_J then \hat{G}_I is known as an *intuitionistic generalized topology* ($\mathcal{J}\hat{G}T$ in short) on \check{X}_J if it meets the criteria listed below:

- 1) $\check{\phi}_I \in \hat{G}_I$.
 - 2) $\cup M_{J_i} \in \hat{G}_I$ for any arbitrary family $\{M_{J_i} : i \in J\} \subseteq \hat{G}_I$.
- The pair (\check{X}_J, \hat{G}_I) is referred to as $\mathcal{J}\hat{G}TS$.

Definition 2.5 [1] Assume that \check{X}_J is a non-empty set and μ_I is the set of $\mathcal{J}S$'s of \check{X}_J then μ_I is known as an *intuitionistic supra topology* ($\mathcal{J}ST$ in short) on \check{X}_J if it meets the criteria listed below:

- 1) $\check{X}_I, \check{\phi}_I \in \mu_I$.
 - 2) $\cup M_{J_i} \in \mu_I$ for any arbitrary family $\{M_{J_i} : i \in J\} \subseteq \mu_I$.
- The pair (\check{X}_J, μ_I) is referred to as $\mathcal{J}STS$.

Definition 2.6 [1] Assume that \check{X}_J is a non-empty set and τ_{II} is the set of $\mathcal{J}S$'s of \check{X}_J then τ_{II} is known as an *intuitionistic infra topology* ($\mathcal{J}IT$ in short) on \check{X}_J if it meets the criteria listed below:

- 1) $\check{X}_I, \check{\phi}_I \in \tau_{II}$.
 - 2) $M_J \cap N_J \in \tau_{II}$ for every $M_J, N_J \in \tau_{II}$.
- The pair (\check{X}_J, τ_{II}) is referred to as $\mathcal{J}ITS$.

Definition 2.7 [1] If (\check{X}_J, τ_I) is a $\mathcal{J}TS$ and M_J is a $\mathcal{J}S$ in \check{X}_J then the definition of the \mathcal{J} -interior operator of M_J ($\mathcal{J}int(M_J)$ in short) and the \mathcal{J} -closure operator of M_J ($\mathcal{J}cl(M_J)$ in short) are as follows:

$$\mathcal{J}int(M_J) = \cup \{N_J : N_J \text{ is } \mathcal{J}OS \text{ in } \check{X}_J \text{ \& } M_J \supseteq N_J\}.$$

$$\mathcal{J}cl(M_J) = \cap \{N_J : N_J \text{ is } \mathcal{J}CS \text{ in } \check{X}_J \text{ \& } M_J \subseteq N_J\}.$$

Definition 2.8 [2] If (\check{X}_J, τ_I) is an $\mathcal{J}TS$ and a $\mathcal{J}S$ M_J is known as the $\mathcal{J}g$ -closed set if $\mathcal{J}cl(M_J) \subseteq U_J$ whenever $M_J \subseteq U_J$ and U_J is $\mathcal{J}OS$ in \check{X}_J . The $\mathcal{J}g$ -open set in \check{X}_J is known as the $\mathcal{J}g$ -closed set's counterpart.

Definition 2.9 [2] If (\check{X}_J, τ_I) is an $\mathcal{J}TS$ and M_J be a $\mathcal{J}S$ in \check{X}_J then the definition of $\mathcal{J}g$ -closure of M_J is, $\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_J) = \cap \{N_J : N_J \text{ is } \mathcal{J}g\text{-CS in } \check{X}_J \text{ \& } M_J \subseteq N_J\}$.

Definition 2.10 [4] If (\check{X}_J, τ_I) is an $\mathcal{J}TS$ and a $\mathcal{J}S$ M_J in \check{X}_J is known as the $\mathcal{J}PO$ set if $M_J \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl(M_J))$. The $\mathcal{J}PC$ set in X is known as the $\mathcal{J}PO$ set's counterpart.

Theorem 2.11 [1] If (\check{X}_J, τ_I) is an $\mathcal{J}TS$ and M_J and N_J are $\mathcal{J}S$'s in \check{X}_J then the followings are hold.

- a) $\mathcal{J}int(\check{\phi}_I) = \check{\phi}_I$ and $\mathcal{J}int(\check{X}_I) = \check{X}_I$.
- b) M_J is an $\mathcal{J}OS$ iff $M_J = \mathcal{J}int(M_J)$.
- c) $M_J \subseteq N_J \Rightarrow \mathcal{J}int(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(N_J)$.
- d) $\mathcal{J}int(M_J \cap N_J) = \mathcal{J}int(M_J) \cap \mathcal{J}int(N_J)$.
- e) $\mathcal{J}int(M_J \cup N_J) \supseteq \mathcal{J}int(M_J) \cup \mathcal{J}int(N_J)$.
- f) $\mathcal{J}cl(\check{\phi}_I) = \check{\phi}_I$ and $\mathcal{J}cl(\check{X}_I) = \check{X}_I$.
- g) M_J is an $\mathcal{J}CS$ iff $M_J = \mathcal{J}cl(M_J)$.
- h) $M_J \subseteq N_J \Rightarrow \mathcal{J}cl(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{J}cl(N_J)$.
- i) $\mathcal{J}cl(M_J \cap N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{J}cl(M_J) \cap \mathcal{J}cl(N_J)$.
- j) $\mathcal{J}cl(M_J \cup N_J) = \mathcal{J}cl(M_J) \cup \mathcal{J}cl(N_J)$.

Theorem 2.12 [2] If (\check{X}_J, τ_I) is an $\mathcal{J}TS$ and M_J, N_J are $\mathcal{J}S$'s in \check{X}_J then the followings are hold.

- a) $\mathcal{J}int^*(\check{\phi}_I) = \check{\phi}_I$ and $\mathcal{J}int^*(\check{X}_I) = \check{X}_I$.
- b) If M_J is $\mathcal{J}g$ -OS then $M_J = \mathcal{J}int^*(M_J)$.

- c) $\mathcal{J}int(M_j) \subseteq \mathcal{J}int^*(M_j) \subseteq M_j$.
- d) $M_j \subseteq N_j \Rightarrow \mathcal{J}int^*(M_j) \subseteq \mathcal{J}int^*(N_j)$.
- e) $\mathcal{J}int^*(M_j \cap N_j) \subseteq \mathcal{J}int^*(M_j) \cap \mathcal{J}int^*(N_j)$.
- f) $\mathcal{J}int^*(M_j \cup N_j) \supseteq \mathcal{J}int^*(M_j) \cup \mathcal{J}int^*(N_j)$.
- g) $\mathcal{J}cl^*(\check{\phi}_I) = \check{\phi}_I$ and $\mathcal{J}cl^*(\check{X}_I) = \check{X}_I$.
- h) If M_j is $\mathcal{J}g$ -CS then $M_j = \mathcal{J}cl^*(M_j)$.
- i) $M_j \subseteq \mathcal{J}cl^*(M_j) \subseteq \mathcal{J}cl(M_j)$.
- j) $M_j \subseteq N_j \Rightarrow \mathcal{J}cl^*(M_j) \subseteq \mathcal{J}cl^*(N_j)$.
- k) $\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_j \cap N_j) \subseteq \mathcal{J}cl^*(M_j) \cap \mathcal{J}cl^*(N_j)$.
- l) $\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_j \cup N_j) \supseteq \mathcal{J}cl^*(M_j) \cup \mathcal{J}cl^*(N_j)$.

Theorem 2.13 [4] If (\check{X}_J, τ_I) is an $\mathcal{J}TS$ and M_j, N_j be a $\mathcal{J}S$'s in \check{X}_J then the followings are hold.

- a) $\mathcal{J}Pint(\check{\phi}_I) = \check{\phi}_I$ and $\mathcal{J}Pint(\check{X}_I) = \check{X}_I$.
- b) M_j is an $\mathcal{J}POS$ iff $M_j = \mathcal{J}Pint(M_j)$.
- c) $M_j \subseteq N_j \Rightarrow \mathcal{J}Pint(M_j) \subseteq \mathcal{J}Pint(N_j)$.
- d) $\mathcal{J}Pint(M_j \cap N_j) = \mathcal{J}Pint(M_j) \cap \mathcal{J}Pint(N_j)$.
- e) $\mathcal{J}Pint(M_j \cup N_j) \supseteq \mathcal{J}Pint(M_j) \cup \mathcal{J}Pint(N_j)$.
- f) $\mathcal{J}Pcl(\check{\phi}_I) = \check{\phi}_I$ and $\mathcal{J}Pcl(\check{X}_I) = \check{X}_I$.
- g) M_j is an $\mathcal{J}PCS$ iff $M_j = \mathcal{J}Pcl(M_j)$.
- h) $M_j \subseteq N_j \Rightarrow \mathcal{J}Pcl(M_j) \subseteq \mathcal{J}Pcl(N_j)$.
- i) $\mathcal{J}Pcl(M_j \cap N_j) \subseteq \mathcal{J}Pcl(M_j) \cap \mathcal{J}Pcl(N_j)$.
- j) $\mathcal{J}Pcl(M_j \cup N_j) = \mathcal{J}Pcl(M_j) \cup \mathcal{J}Pcl(N_j)$.

Theorem 2.14 [1,2,4] If (\check{X}_J, τ_{IT}) is an $\mathcal{J}TS$ and M_j is a $\mathcal{J}S$ of \check{X}_J , then,

- a) $\mathcal{J}int(M_j^c) = [\mathcal{J}cl(M_j)]^c$ and $\mathcal{J}cl(M_j^c) = [\mathcal{J}int(M_j)]^c$.
- b) $\mathcal{J}int^*(M_j^c) = [\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_j)]^c$ and $\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_j^c) = [\mathcal{J}int^*(M_j)]^c$.
- c) $\mathcal{J}Pint(M_j^c) = [\mathcal{J}Pcl(M_j)]^c$ and $\mathcal{J}Pcl(M_j^c) = [\mathcal{J}Pint(M_j)]^c$.

3. Intuitionistic Pre * Open Sets

We define the following definitions

Definition 3.1 If (\check{X}_J, τ_{IT}) is an $\mathcal{J}TS$ and M_j is an $\mathcal{J}S$ then M_j is referred to intuitionistic pre * open ($\mathcal{J}P^*O$ in short) set if $M_j \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_j))$. $\mathcal{J}P^*O(\check{X}_J)$ stands for the family of all $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ sets in (\check{X}_J, τ_{IT}) .

Example 3.2 Let $\check{X}_J = \{a_{xj}, b_{xj}, c_{xj}\}$ and $\tau_I = \{\check{X}_I, \check{\phi}_I, \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}\}, \{b_{xj}, c_{xj}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{b_{xj}\}, \{a_{xj}, c_{xj}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}, b_{xj}\}, \{c_{xj}\} \rangle\}$ then $\mathcal{J}P^*O(\check{X}_J) = \{\check{X}_I, \check{\phi}_I, \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}\}, \{b_{xj}, c_{xj}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}, b_{xj}\}, \{c_{xj}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{b_{xj}\}, \{a_{xj}, c_{xj}\} \rangle\}$.

Remark 3.3 \check{X}_I and $\check{\phi}_I$ are always $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set.

Theorem 3.4 Arbitrary union of $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ sets is $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set in $\mathcal{J}TS$.

Proof: Suppose $\{M_{j\alpha} / \alpha \in I\}$ is a family of $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set in $\mathcal{J}TS$. Then for each α , $M_{j\alpha} \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_{j\alpha}))$. Since $M_{j\alpha} \subseteq \cup M_{j\alpha}$ then $\mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_{j\alpha})) \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(\cup M_{j\alpha}))$ and also $M_{j\alpha} \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(\cup M_{j\alpha}))$. Therefore, $\cup M_{j\alpha} \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(\cup M_{j\alpha}))$. Hence $\cup M_{j\alpha}$ is $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set.

Remark 3.5 Intersection of two $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ sets need not be a $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set.

Example 3.6 Let $\check{X}_J = \{a_{xj}, b_{xj}, c_{xj}\}$ and $\tau_I = \{\check{X}_I, \check{\phi}_I, \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}\}, \{c_{xj}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{c_{xj}\}, \{a_{xj}, b_{xj}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}, c_{xj}\}, \phi_{xj} \rangle\}$ then $\mathcal{J}P^*O(\check{X}_J) = \{\check{X}_I, \check{\phi}_I, \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}\}, \{c_{xj}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{c_{xj}\}, \{a_{xj}, b_{xj}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}\}, \phi_{xj} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}, c_{xj}\}, \phi_{xj} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}\}, \{b_{xj}, c_{xj}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}, c_{xj}\}, \{b_{xj}\} \rangle\}$. Here, $\langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}\}, \phi_{xj} \rangle \cap \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}, c_{xj}\}, \{b_{xj}\} \rangle = \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}\}, \{b_{xj}\} \rangle \notin \mathcal{J}P^*O(\check{X}_J)$.

Remark 3.7 The Difference between two $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ sets need not be $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set.

Example 3.8 In 3.6, Take $M_j = \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}\}, \{c_{xj}\} \rangle$ and $N_j = \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{xj}, c_{xj}\}, \{b_{xj}\} \rangle$ then $M_j - N_j = M_j \cap N_j^c = \langle \check{X}_J, \phi_{xj}, \{a_{xj}, c_{xj}\} \rangle$ is not a $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set.

Remark 3.9 Assuming that \check{X}_J is a non-empty set and $\mathcal{J}P^*O(\check{X}_J)$ is a set of all $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set of \check{X}_J then,

- 1) $(\check{X}_J, \mathcal{J}P^*O(\check{X}_J))$ no need to form a $\mathcal{J}TS$.
- 2) $(\check{X}_J, \mathcal{J}P^*O(\check{X}_J))$ is a $\mathcal{J}GTS$.

- 3) $(\tilde{X}_J, \mathcal{I}P^*O(\tilde{X}_J))$ is a $\mathcal{I}STS$.
- 4) $(\tilde{X}_J, \mathcal{I}P^*O(\tilde{X}_J))$ no need to form a $\mathcal{I}TS$.

Proof: By 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5 we get the results.

Lemma 3.10 Let M_J and N_J are $\mathcal{I}S$'s in \tilde{X}_J , then $\mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J) \cap N_J \subseteq \mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J \cap N_J)$ if N_J is $\mathcal{I}O$ set.

Theorem 3.11 Intersection of two $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ sets is $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set if one of which is $\mathcal{I}O$ set.

Proof: Suppose M_J & N_J are $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ sets in (\tilde{X}_J, τ_I) and N_J is $\mathcal{I}O$ set, then $M_J \subseteq \mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J))$ & $N_J = \mathcal{I}int(N_J)$. Now $M_J \cap N_J \subseteq \mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J)) \cap \mathcal{I}int(N_J) = \mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J) \cap N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J \cap N_J))$. By 3.10, Hence $M_J \cap N_J$ is $\mathcal{I}P^*OS$.

Theorem 3.12 Let (\tilde{X}_J, τ_I) be an $\mathcal{I}TS$, M_J be an $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set and N_J be an intuitionistic set such that $N_J \subseteq M_J \subseteq \mathcal{I}cl^*(N_J)$ then N_J is also an $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set.

Proof: Suppose M_J is an $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set then $M_J \subseteq \mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J))$. Since, $M_J \subseteq \mathcal{I}cl^*(N_J)$ then $\mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{I}cl^*(N_J)$. Also $N_J \subseteq M_J$ then $N_J \subseteq \mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl^*(N_J))$. Hence N_J is $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set.

Theorem 3.13 Every $\mathcal{I}O$ set is $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set in $\mathcal{I}TS$.

Proof: Let M_J be a $\mathcal{I}O$ set then $M_J = \mathcal{I}int(M_J)$. Always $M_J \subseteq \mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J) \Rightarrow \mathcal{I}int(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J)) \Rightarrow M_J \subseteq \mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J))$. Hence M_J is $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set.

According to the example below, the reverse part of the aforementioned theorem no need to true.

Example 3.14 Take $\tilde{X}_J = \{a_{x_j}, b_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\}$ and $\tau_I = \{\check{X}_I, \check{\phi}_I, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \{a_{x_j}\}, \{b_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \{b_{x_j}\}, \{c_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \phi_{x_j}, \{b_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{a_{x_j}, b_{x_j}\}, \phi_{x_j} \rangle\}$ then $\mathcal{I}P^*O(\tilde{X}_J) = \{\check{X}_I, \check{\phi}_I, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \phi_{x_j}, \{b_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{a_{x_j}\}, \{b_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \{b_{x_j}\}, \{c_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{a_{x_j}, b_{x_j}\}, \phi_{x_j} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{a_{x_j}\}, \{b_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{a_{x_j}, b_{x_j}\}, \{c_{x_j}\} \rangle\}$. Here, $\langle \check{X}_I, \{a_{x_j}\}, \{b_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\} \rangle$ is $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set but not a $\mathcal{I}O$ set.

Theorem 3.15 Every $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set is $\mathcal{I}PO$ set in $\mathcal{I}TS$.

Proof: Let M_J be an $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set then $M_J \subseteq \mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J))$. Always $\mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{I}cl(M_J) \Rightarrow \mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl^*(M_J)) \subseteq \mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl(M_J)) \Rightarrow M_J \subseteq \mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl(M_J))$. Hence M_J is $\mathcal{I}PO$ set.

According to the example below, the reverse part of the aforementioned theorem no need to true.

Example 3.16 Take $\tilde{X}_J = \{a_{x_j}, b_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\}$ and $\tau_I = \{\check{X}_I, \check{\phi}_I, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \{b_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \phi_{x_j}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \{b_{x_j}\}, \phi_{x_j} \rangle, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \{b_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \{b_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\}, \phi_{x_j} \rangle\}$ then $\mathcal{I}P^*O(\tilde{X}_J) = \tau_I$ and $\mathcal{I}PO(\tilde{X}_J) = \{\check{X}_I, \check{\phi}_I, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \phi_{x_j}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \phi_{x_j}, \{a_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \{c_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{b_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \tilde{X}_J, \{b_{x_j}\}, \{c_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{b_{x_j}\}, \phi_{x_j} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{c_{x_j}\}, \phi_{x_j} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{a_{x_j}, b_{x_j}\}, \phi_{x_j} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{b_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\}, \phi_{x_j} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{a_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\}, \phi_{x_j} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{b_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{c_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}, b_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{b_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{a_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\}, \{b_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_I, \{a_{x_j}, b_{x_j}\}, \{c_{x_j}\} \rangle\}$. Here, $\langle \check{X}_I, \{a_{x_j}\}, \{c_{x_j}\} \rangle$ is $\mathcal{I}POS$ but not a $\mathcal{I}P^*OS$.

Remark 3.17 The relationship between the $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set, $\mathcal{I}O$ set and $\mathcal{I}PO$ set is depicted in the diagram below.

Theorem 3.18 $\mathcal{I}O(\tilde{X}_J, \tau_I) \subseteq \mathcal{I}P^*O(\tilde{X}_J, \tau_I) \subseteq \mathcal{I}PO(\tilde{X}_J, \tau_I)$ in $\mathcal{I}TS(\tilde{X}_J, \tau_I)$.

Proof: Let $M_J \in \mathcal{I}O(\tilde{X}_J, \tau_I)$ then M_J is $\mathcal{I}OS$ in (\tilde{X}_J, τ_I) . Since every $\mathcal{I}OS$ is $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set and every $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set is $\mathcal{I}PO$ set then M_J is $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set and $\mathcal{I}PO$ set. Hence $M_J \in \mathcal{I}P^*O(\tilde{X}_J, \tau_I)$ and $M_J \in \mathcal{I}PO(\tilde{X}_J, \tau_I)$.

Theorem 3.19 If M_J is a $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set and N_J is a $\mathcal{I}OS$ then $M_J \cup N_J$ is $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set.

Proof: Since every $\mathcal{I}OS$ is $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ then N_J is $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set. By 3.4, $M_J \cup N_J$ is $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set.

4. Intuitionistic Pre * Closed Sets

Definition 4.1 If (\tilde{X}_J, τ_{IT}) is an $\mathcal{I}TS$ and M_J is an $\mathcal{I}S$ then M_J is said to be an intuitionistic pre * closed (in short $\mathcal{I}P^*C$) set if M_J^c is $\mathcal{I}P^*OS$. $\mathcal{I}P^*C(\tilde{X}_J)$ stands for the family of $\mathcal{I}P^*C$ sets in (\tilde{X}_J, τ_{IT}) .

Example 4.2 In 3.2, $\mathcal{P}^*C(\check{X}_J) = \{\check{X}_J, \check{\Phi}_J, \langle \check{X}_J, \{a_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\}, \{b_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{c_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}, b_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{b_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle\}$.

Remark 4.3 \check{X}_J and $\check{\Phi}_J$ are always \mathcal{P}^*C sets.

Theorem 4.4 Let be an \mathcal{JTS} and M_J be a \mathcal{J} in \check{X} then M_J is \mathcal{P}^*C set iff $\mathcal{J}cl(\mathcal{J}int^*(M_J)) \subseteq M_J$.

Proof: Let M_J be an \mathcal{P}^*C set $\Leftrightarrow M_J^c$ is \mathcal{P}^*O set $\Leftrightarrow M_J^c \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_J^c)) \Leftrightarrow M_J \supseteq [\mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_J^c))]^c \Leftrightarrow M_J \supseteq \mathcal{J}cl[\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_J^c)]^c \Leftrightarrow M_J \supseteq \mathcal{J}cl(\mathcal{J}int^*[M_J^c]^c) \Leftrightarrow M_J \supseteq \mathcal{J}cl(\mathcal{J}int^*(M_J))$.

Theorem 4.5 In \mathcal{JTS} , Intersection of \mathcal{P}^*C sets is \mathcal{P}^*CS .

Proof: Let M_J and N_J are \mathcal{P}^*CS 's then M_J^c and N_J^c are \mathcal{P}^*O sets. Therefore, $M_J^c \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_J^c))$ and $N_J^c \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(N_J^c))$. Now, $(M_J \cap N_J)^c = M_J^c \cup N_J^c \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_J^c)) \cup \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(N_J^c)) \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_J^c) \cup \mathcal{J}cl^*(N_J^c)) \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_J^c \cup N_J^c)) = \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_J \cap N_J)^c)$ then $(M_J \cap N_J)^c$ is \mathcal{P}^*OS . Hence, $M_J \cap N_J$ is \mathcal{P}^*C set.

Remark 4.6 Union of two \mathcal{P}^*C sets need not be a \mathcal{P}^*C set.

Example 4.7 In 3.6, $\langle \check{X}_J, \phi_{x_j}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle, \langle \check{X}_J, \{b_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\} \rangle \in \mathcal{P}^*C(\check{X}_J)$ but $\langle \check{X}_J, \phi_{x_j}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle \cup \langle \check{X}_J, \{b_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\} \rangle = \langle \check{X}_J, \{b_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle \notin \mathcal{P}^*C(\check{X}_J)$.

Remark 4.8 The Difference between two \mathcal{P}^*C sets need not be \mathcal{P}^*C set.

Example 4.9 In 3.6, Take $M_J = \langle \check{X}_J, \{c_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle, N_J = \langle \check{X}_J, \{b_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\} \rangle \in \mathcal{P}^*C(\check{X}_J)$ then $M_J - N_J = M_J \cap N_J^c = \langle \check{X}_J, \{c_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}, b_{x_j}\} \rangle \notin \mathcal{P}^*C(\check{X}_J)$.

Remark 4.10 Let \check{X}_J be a non-empty set and $\mathcal{P}^*C(\check{X}_J)$ be a set of all \mathcal{P}^*C sets of \check{X}_J then,

- 1) $(\check{X}_J, \mathcal{P}^*C(\check{X}_J))$ no need to form a \mathcal{JTS} .
- 2) $(\check{X}_J, \mathcal{P}^*C(\check{X}_J))$ no need to form a \mathcal{JGTS} .
- 3) $(\check{X}_J, \mathcal{P}^*C(\check{X}_J))$ no need to form a \mathcal{JSTS} .
- 4) $(\check{X}_J, \mathcal{P}^*C(\check{X}_J))$ is a \mathcal{JITS} .

Proof: By 4.3, 4.5 and 4.6 we get the results.

Theorem 4.11 Union of two \mathcal{P}^*C sets is \mathcal{P}^*C set if one of which is $\mathcal{J}C$ set.

Proof: If \check{A} is \mathcal{P}^*C set in (\check{X}_J, τ_J) then M_J^c is \mathcal{P}^*O set. Suppose N_J is $\mathcal{J}C$ set then N_J^c is $\mathcal{J}O$ set. By 3.11, $M_J^c \cap N_J^c$ is \mathcal{P}^*O set. Therefore $(M_J \cup N_J)^c$ is \mathcal{P}^*O set. Hence, $M_J \cup N_J$ is \mathcal{P}^*C set.

Theorem 4.12 If (\check{X}_J, τ_J) is an \mathcal{JTS} , M_J is an \mathcal{P}^*C set and N_J is an $\mathcal{J}S$ such that $\mathcal{J}int^*(N_J) \subseteq M_J \subseteq N_J$ then N_J is also an \mathcal{P}^*C set.

Proof: Suppose M_J is \mathcal{P}^*C set then M_J^c is \mathcal{P}^*O set. Therefore, $M_J^c \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_J^c))$. Since, $\mathcal{J}int^*(N_J) \subseteq M_J$ then $\mathcal{J}int^*(N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{J}int^*(M_J) \Rightarrow \mathcal{J}cl^*(M_J^c) \subseteq \mathcal{J}cl^*(N_J^c)$. Also $M_J \subseteq N_J$ then $N_J^c \subseteq M_J^c$. Therefore, $N_J^c \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(M_J^c)) \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}cl^*(N_J^c)) \Rightarrow N_J^c$ is \mathcal{P}^*O set. Hence, N_J is \mathcal{P}^*C set.

Theorem 4.13 Let (\check{X}_J, τ_J) be an \mathcal{JTS} , M_J be an \mathcal{P}^*O set and N_J be an \mathcal{P}^*C set then,

- a) $M_J \cup N_J^c$ is \mathcal{P}^*O set.
- b) $M_J^c \cap N_J$ is \mathcal{P}^*C set.

Proof: (a) Suppose M_J is a \mathcal{P}^*O set and N_J is an \mathcal{P}^*C set then M_J and N_J^c are \mathcal{P}^*O set. By theorem – 3.4, $M_J \cup N_J^c$ is \mathcal{P}^*O set. (b) Let M_J be an \mathcal{P}^*O set and N_J be an \mathcal{P}^*C set then M_J^c and N_J are \mathcal{P}^*C sets. By theorem – 4.5, $M_J^c \cap N_J$ is \mathcal{P}^*C set.

Theorem 4.14 Let (\check{X}_J, τ_J) be an \mathcal{JTS} , M_J be an \mathcal{P}^*O set and N_J be an \mathcal{P}^*C set then the followings are equivalent,

- a) $M_J \cup N_J^c$ is \mathcal{P}^*O set.
- b) $M_J^c \cap N_J$ is \mathcal{P}^*C set.
- c) $N_J - M_J$ is \mathcal{P}^*C set.

Proof: (a) \Rightarrow (b), Let $M_J \cup N_J^c$ is \mathcal{P}^*O set then $(M_J \cup N_J^c)^c$ is \mathcal{P}^*C set. Hence, $M_J^c \cap N_J$ is \mathcal{P}^*C set. (b) \Rightarrow (c), Let $M_J^c \cap N_J$ is \mathcal{P}^*C set then $N_J \cap M_J^c$ is also \mathcal{P}^*C set. Hence, $N_J - M_J$ is \mathcal{P}^*C set. (c) \Rightarrow (a), Let $N_J - M_J$ is \mathcal{P}^*C set then $(N_J - M_J)^c$ is \mathcal{P}^*O set. Hence, $(N_J \cap M_J^c)^c = N_J^c \cup M_J = M_J \cup N_J^c$ is \mathcal{P}^*O set.

Theorem 4.15 Every $\mathcal{J}C$ set is $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ set in $\mathcal{J}TS$.

Proof: If M_J is $\mathcal{J}C$ set then M_J^c is $\mathcal{J}O$ set. By theorem – 3.13, M_J^c is $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set. Hence M_J is $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ set.

According to the example below, the reverse part of the aforementioned theorem no need to true.

Example 4.16 In 3.14, $\langle \check{X}_J, \{b_{x_j}, c_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle$ is $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ set but not a $\mathcal{J}C$ set.

Theorem 4.17 Every $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ set is $\mathcal{J}PC$ set in $\mathcal{J}TS$.

Proof: Suppose M_J is $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ set then M_J^c is $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set. By theorem – 3.15, M_J^c is $\mathcal{J}PO$ set. Hence M_J is $\mathcal{J}PC$ set. The converse of the aforementioned theorem need not be true.

Example 4.18 In example – 3.16, $\langle \check{X}_J, \{c_{x_j}\}, \{a_{x_j}\} \rangle$ is $\mathcal{J}PC$ set but not a $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ set.

Remark 4.19 The relationship of the $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ set with $\mathcal{J}C$ set and $\mathcal{J}PC$ set is depicted in the diagram below.

Theorem 4.20 $\mathcal{J}C(\check{X}_J, \tau_1) \subseteq \mathcal{J}P^*C(\check{X}_J, \tau_1) \subseteq \mathcal{J}PC(\check{X}_J, \tau_1)$ in $\mathcal{J}TS(\check{X}_J, \tau_1)$.

Proof: If $M_J \in \mathcal{J}C(\check{X}_J, \tau_1)$ then M_J is $\mathcal{J}C$ set in (\check{X}_J, τ_1) . Since every $\mathcal{J}C$ set is $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ set and every $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ set is $\mathcal{J}PC$ set then M_J is $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ set and $\mathcal{J}PC$ set. Hence $M_J \in \mathcal{J}P^*C(\check{X}_J, \tau_1)$ and $M_J \in \mathcal{J}PC(\check{X}_J, \tau_1)$.

Theorem 4.21 If M_J is a $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ set and N_J is $\mathcal{J}CS$ then $M_J \cap N_J$ is $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ set.

Proof: Since every $\mathcal{J}CS$ is $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ then N_J is a $\mathcal{J}P^*CS$. By 4.5, $M_J \cap N_J$ is $\mathcal{J}P^*C$ set.

5. Intuitionistic Pre * Interior and Intuitionistic Pre * Closure Operator

Definition 5.1 Assume that (\check{X}_J, τ_1) is an $\mathcal{J}TS$. The intuitionistic pre * interior of M_J is the union of all $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ sets of (\check{X}_J, τ_1) included in M_J and is indicated by $\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J)$. (i.e) $\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J) = \cup \{N_J / N_J \subseteq M_J \ \& \ N_J \text{ is } \mathcal{J}P^*O \text{ set}\}$.

Theorem 5.2 In $\mathcal{J}TS(\check{X}_J, \tau_1)$, $\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J)$ is the largest $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set contained in M_J .

Proof: Is implied by 5.1 & 3.4.

Theorem 5.3 If (\check{X}_J, τ_1) is an $\mathcal{J}TS$ then a $\mathcal{J}S$ M_J is $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set iff $\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J) = M_J$.

Proof: Suppose M_J is $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set then $\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J) = M_J$ is evident, conversely, If $\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J) = M_J$ then by 5.2, $\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J)$ is $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set. Hence, M_J is $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set.

Theorem 5.4 If (\check{X}_J, τ_1) is an $\mathcal{J}TS$ and M_J is a $\mathcal{J}S$ then the followings are hold.

- $\mathcal{J}P^*int(\check{\Phi}_I) = \check{\Phi}_I$.
- $\mathcal{J}P^*int(\check{X}_I) = \check{X}_I$.
- $\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J) \subseteq M_J$.
- $\mathcal{J}P^*int(\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J)) = \mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J)$.
- $\mathcal{J}int(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{J}Pint(M_J) \subseteq M_J$.
- $\mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J)) = \mathcal{J}int(M_J)$.
- $\mathcal{J}P^*int(\mathcal{J}int(M_J)) = \mathcal{J}int(M_J)$.

Proof:

(a) Since, $\check{\Phi}_I$ is $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set then by 5.3, $\mathcal{J}P^*int(\check{\Phi}_I) = \check{\Phi}_I$.

(b) Since, \check{X}_I is $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set then by 5.3, $\mathcal{J}P^*int(\check{X}_I) = \check{X}_I$.

(c) By theorem – 5.2, $\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J) \subseteq M_J$.

(d) Since, $\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J)$ is $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set then by 5.3, $\mathcal{J}P^*int(\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J)) = \mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J)$.

(e) By theorem – 3.11, 3.13 and 3.15, $\mathcal{J}int(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{J}Pint(M_J) \subseteq M_J$ is obvious.

(f) Since, $\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J) \subseteq M_J$ then $\mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J)) \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(M_J)$. By (e), $\mathcal{J}int(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J)$ then $\mathcal{J}int(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J))$. Hence, $\mathcal{J}int(\mathcal{J}P^*int(M_J)) = \mathcal{J}int(M_J)$.

(g) Since, $\mathcal{J}int(M_J)$ is $\mathcal{J}O$ set then $\mathcal{J}int(M_J)$ is $\mathcal{J}P^*O$ set then by 5.3, $\mathcal{J}P^*int(\mathcal{J}int(M_J)) = \mathcal{J}int(M_J)$.

Theorem 5.5 If (\tilde{X}_J, τ_J) is an \mathcal{JTS} and M_J and N_J are \mathcal{JS} 's then the followings are hold.

- a) If $M_J \subseteq N_J$ then $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(N_J)$.
- b) $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J \cup N_J) \supseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J) \cup \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(N_J)$.
- c) $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J \cap N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J) \cap \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(N_J)$.

Proof:

- (a) Suppose $M_J \subseteq N_J$ then by 5.1, $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(N_J)$ is obvious.
- (b) Since, $M_J \subseteq M_J \cup N_J$ and $N_J \subseteq M_J \cup N_J$ then by (a), $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J \cup N_J)$ and $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J \cup N_J)$. Hence, $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J \cup N_J) \supseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J) \cup \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(N_J)$.
- (c) Since, $M_J \cap N_J \subseteq M_J$ and $M_J \cap N_J \subseteq N_J$ then by (a), $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J \cap N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J)$ and $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J \cap N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(N_J)$. Hence, $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J \cap N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J) \cap \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(N_J)$.

Definition 5.6 Assume that (\tilde{X}_J, τ_J) is an \mathcal{JTS} . The intuitionistic pre * closure of M_J is denoted by $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J)$ and it is the intersection of all $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{C}$ sets of (\tilde{X}_J, τ_J) containing M_J . (i.e) $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) = \bigcap \{N_J / N_J \supseteq M_J \ \& \ N_J \text{ is } \mathcal{JP}^*\text{C set}\}$.

Theorem 5.7 $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J)$ is the smallest $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{C}$ set containing M_J in $\mathcal{JTS} (\tilde{X}_J, \tau_J)$.

Proof: Is implied by definition – (5.6) and theorem – (4.5).

Theorem 5.8 If (\tilde{X}_J, τ_J) is an \mathcal{JTS} then the $\mathcal{JS} M_J$ is $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{C}$ set iff $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) = M_J$.

Proof: Suppose M_J is a $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{C}$ set then $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) = M_J$ is obvious, conversely, Suppose $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) = M_J$ then by 5.7, $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J)$ is $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{C}$. Hence, M_J is $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{C}$.

Theorem 5.9 If (\tilde{X}_J, τ_J) is an \mathcal{JTS} and M_J is a \mathcal{JS} of \tilde{X}_J , then

- a) $[\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J)]^c = \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J^c)$.
- b) $[\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J)]^c = \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J^c)$.

Proof: (a) Let $p \in [\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J)]^c$ then $p \notin \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J)$ (i.e), $p \notin$ any $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{O}$ subset of M_J . Let E_J be an $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{C}$ set containing M_J^c . (i.e), $M_J^c \subseteq E_J$ and E_J is $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{CS}$ then E_J^c is $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{OS}$ and $E_J^c \subseteq M_J$. Therefore, $p \notin E_J^c \Rightarrow p \in E_J \Rightarrow p \in \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J^c)$. Hence, $[\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J)]^c \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J^c)$. Conversely, let $p \in \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J^c)$ then $p \in$ every $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{CS}$ containing $M_J^c \Rightarrow p \notin$ any $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{OS}$ contained in M_J . (i.e), $p \notin \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J) \Rightarrow p \in [\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J)]^c$. Therefore, $[\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J)]^c \supseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J^c)$. Hence, $[\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(M_J)]^c = \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J^c)$.

(b) It is similar to (a).

Theorem 5.10 If (\tilde{X}_J, τ_J) is an \mathcal{JTS} and M_J is a \mathcal{JS} then the followings are hold.

- a) $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(\check{\Phi}_J) = \check{\Phi}_J$.
- b) $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(\check{X}_J) = \check{X}_J$.
- c) $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) \supseteq M_J$.
- d) $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J)) = \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J)$.
- e) $M_J \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{Jcl}(M_J)$.
- f) $\mathcal{Jcl}(\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J)) = \mathcal{Jcl}(M_J)$.
- g) $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(\mathcal{Jcl}(M_J)) = \mathcal{Jcl}(M_J)$.

Proof:

- (a) Since, $\check{\Phi}_J$ is $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{C}$ then by theorem – 5.8, $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(\check{\Phi}_J) = \check{\Phi}_J$.
- (b) Since, \check{X}_J is $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{C}$ then by theorem – 5.8, $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(\check{X}_J) = \check{X}_J$.
- (c) By theorem – 5.7, $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) \supseteq M_J$.
- (d) Since, $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J)$ is $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{C}$ set then by theorem – 5.8, $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J)) = \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J)$.
- (e) By theorem – 5.4, $\mathcal{Jint}(N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(N_J)$, $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(N_J)$ and $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{int}(N_J) \subseteq N_J$ then $\mathcal{Jcl}(N_J^c) \supseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(N_J^c)$, $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(N_J^c) \supseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(N_J^c)$ and $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(N_J^c) \supseteq N_J^c$. Taking, $M_J = N_J^c$. Hence, $M_J \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{Jcl}(M_J)$.
- (f) Since, $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) \supseteq M_J$ then $\mathcal{Jcl}(\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J)) \supseteq \mathcal{Jcl}(M_J)$. By (e), $\mathcal{Jcl}(M_J) \supseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J)$ then $\mathcal{Jcl}(M_J) \supseteq \mathcal{Jcl}(\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J))$. Hence, $\mathcal{Jcl}(\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J)) = \mathcal{Jcl}(M_J)$.
- (g) Since, $\mathcal{Jcl}(M_J)$ is \mathcal{JCS} then $\mathcal{Jcl}(M_J)$ is $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{CS}$ then by theorem – 5.8, $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(\mathcal{Jcl}(M_J)) = \mathcal{Jcl}(M_J)$.

Theorem 5.11 If (\tilde{X}_J, τ_J) is an \mathcal{JTS} and M_J and N_J are \mathcal{JS} 's then the followings are hold.

- a) If $M_J \subseteq N_J$ then $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(N_J)$.
- b) $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J \cup N_J) \supseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) \cup \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(N_J)$.
- c) $\mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J \cap N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(M_J) \cap \mathcal{JP}^*\text{cl}(N_J)$.

Proof:

(a) Suppose $M_J \subseteq N_J$ then by 5.6, $\mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{I}P^*cl(N_J)$ is obvious.

(b) Since, $M_J \subseteq M_J \cup N_J$ and $N_J \subseteq M_J \cup N_J$ then by (a), $\mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J \cup N_J)$ and $\mathcal{I}P^*cl(N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J \cup N_J)$. Hence, $\mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J \cup N_J) \supseteq \mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J) \cup \mathcal{I}P^*cl(N_J)$.

(c) Since, $M_J \cap N_J \subseteq M_J$ and $M_J \cap N_J \subseteq N_J$ then by (a), $\mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J \cap N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J)$ and $\mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J \cap N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{I}P^*cl(N_J)$. Hence, $\mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J \cap N_J) \subseteq \mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J) \cap \mathcal{I}P^*cl(N_J)$.

Theorem 5.12. Let (\tilde{X}_J, τ_J) be an $\mathcal{I}TS$ and M_J be an $\mathcal{I}S$ of \tilde{X}_J and $m_{x_j} \in \tilde{X}_J$. Then $m_{x_j} \in \mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J)$ iff every $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set in \tilde{X}_J containing m intersects M_J .

Proof: Suppose $m_{x_j} \notin \mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J)$ then $m_{x_j} \in [\mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J)]^c$. (i.e), $[\mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J)]^c$ is an $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set in \tilde{X}_J containing m_{x_j} that does not intersects M_J . Conversely, Suppose M_J is an $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set in \tilde{X}_J containing m that does not intersects M_J then $\mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J) \subseteq M^c$. Hence, $m \notin \mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J)$.

Theorem 5.13. Let (\tilde{X}_J, τ_J) be an $\mathcal{I}TS$ and M_J be an $\mathcal{I}S$ of \tilde{X}_J . Then $\mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J)) = \phi_I$ if M_J is intuitionistic nowhere dense set in \tilde{X}_J .

Proof: Let M_J is intuitionistic nowhere dense set in \tilde{X}_J . Then $\mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl(M_J)) = \check{\phi}_I$. Since, $\mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J) \subseteq \mathcal{I}cl(M_J)$. Therefore, $\mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J)) \subseteq \mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}cl(M_J)) = \check{\phi}_I$. Hence, $\mathcal{I}int(\mathcal{I}P^*cl(M_J)) = \check{\phi}_I$.

6. Conclusions

We discussed the $\mathcal{I}P^*O$ set, $\mathcal{I}P^*C$ set, $\mathcal{I}P^*int$ of set, and $\mathcal{I}P^*cl$ of set in this paper. We intend to conduct research in the future on $\mathcal{I}P^*$ continuous functions, $\mathcal{I}P^*$ separated, $\mathcal{I}P^*$ connected sets, $\mathcal{I}P^*$ compact and so on.

References

1. D. Coker, An Introduction to Intuitionistic Topological Spaces, Busefal81, 2000, 51 -56.
2. G. Esther Rathinakani and M. Navaneethakrishnan, "A New Closure Operator in Intuitionistic Topological Spaces."
3. G. Esther Rathinakani and M. Navaneethakrishnan, "A Study on Intuitionistic Semi * Open Set." Design Engineering (2021): 5043-5049.
4. G. Sasikala and M. Navaneetha Krishnan "On Intuitionistic pre Open Sets", International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, Volume 119, No. 15, 2018.